

Effect of Process Parameters on Thermal Conductivity and Temperature History in Extrusion-Deposition Additive Manufacturing

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Extrusion-based large-format additive manufacturing (LFAM)

- Advantages of extrusion-based LFAM
 - **High deposition rate:** up to 86 kg per hour using the thermoplastic extrusion process.
 - **Processability:** facilitates the manufacturing of large-scale structures efficiently.
 - **Cost reduction:** significantly lowers tooling costs.
 - **Enhanced properties:** offers superior thermal and mechanical properties with diverse options of engineering plastics and reinforcements.

BAAM system; 1) Printing chamber (6m length x 2.5m width x 1.8m height), 2) Single screw polymer extrusion deposition head, 3) Gantry system, and 4) Control station¹

Ingersoll – MasterPrint 3x by UMaine (30.5m length x 18.3m width x 3m height)²

¹A. A. Hassen, et.al., “The Durability of Large-Scale Additive Manufacturing Composite Molds,” in *CAMX 2016*, 2016.

²<https://composites.umaine.edu/facilities/additive-manufacturing/>

Applications of extrusion-based LFAM

Electric vehicle, “Olli”
(Local Motors)¹

Marine, “A boat -
3Dirigo” (UMaine)²

Aerospace, “trim-and-
drill tool for aircraft
component” (ORNL)³

3D-printed House with
bio-based materials
(UMaine)⁴

¹Kirsten K., “Meet Olli 2.0, a 3D-printed autonomous shuttle,” 2021.

²UMaine news, “World Records related to largest 3D printer,” 2019.

³Office of Technology Transitions, “3D printed tool for building aircraft achieves Guinness World Records Title,” 2016.

⁴Joan F., et al., “Research report: R1 Global Impact – Local Relevance,” University of Maine: Orono, ME, USA, 2023.

Challenges and key factors in extrusion-based LFAM

- Challenges

- **Structural stability:** risk of failure or warpage.
- **Skilled labor dependence:** heavily rely on the experience of skilled operators.
- **Manufacturing variances:** variability in material, geometry, process parameters, toolpath.
- **Anisotropic material behavior:** material properties highly dependent on the toolpath.

- Key factors

- **Temperature history:** the structural stability and defect are determined by temperature.
- **Layer deposition time (layer time):** the total time required for a layer to be deposited.

Failure cases

Objectives and material

- Objectives:
 - Objective 1: Evaluating the effect of bead overlap distance on thermal conductivity.
 - Objective 2: Evaluating the effect of bead geometry on temperature history during the manufacturing.
 - Objective 3: Sensitivity analysis of thermal conductivity, heat capacity and thermal expansion coefficient on temperature and deformation history.
- Material:
 - Wood flour reinforced amorphous polylactic acid (compound of NatureWorks aPLA 3D700 and American Wood Flours 100 mesh Northern Yellow Pine)

Objective 1
Effect of bead overlap distance
on thermal conductivity

Objective 2
Effect of bead geometry
on thermal history

Objective 3
Sensitivity analysis of properties on
temperature & deformation history

Objective 1:

Evaluating the effect of bead overlap distance on thermal conductivity.

Specimen fabrication

- Base line specimen is manufactured using compression molding at 180 °C and 50 bar.
- Box print with simple raster pattern using different bead overlap distance.
 - 6 steps of overlap: 5%, 8%, 10%, 11% and 14%
- Thermal conductivity measurement in anisotropic direction (x, y, z – direction)
 - Printing direction is defined as x-direction

Box print geometry print

Sample geometry:

Prepared specimen for thermal conductivity measurement

- Baseline specimen

- Specimens with different overlap distance in x, y, z direction.

5% overlap – x direction

5% overlap – z direction

14% overlap – x direction

14% overlap – z direction

Heat capacity and thermal conductivity measurement

- Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)
 - Specific heat, glass transition temperature
- Transient plane source (TPS)
 - Thermal conductivity

DSC

TPS

TPS test set up

- TPS test conditions
 - 6 mm sensor
 - Test time: 40 seconds
 - Power: 0.02 W

6 mm sensor

Sensor installation

TPS test results

- Thermal conductivity (κ , W/mK)

$$\kappa = \alpha \cdot \rho \cdot C_p$$

α : diffusivity (m^2/s), ρ : density (kg/m^3)

C_p : specific heat (J/kgK)

- Specific heat: $1,350 J/kgK$ (@ $25^\circ C$)

Objective 2:

Evaluating the effect of bead geometry on temperature history during the manufacturing.

Temperature measurement during P-shape print

- Geometry: Multi-beads wall geometry with 60 layers
 - Half (one bead) : Half (two beads)
- Temperature measurement using an Infrared (IR) camera
 - IR camera: FLIR Boson, FOV: 0.4m x 0.32m
- Bead geometries:

Bead geometry	Nozzle Diameter (mm)	Width (mm)	Height (mm)
# 1	4	6	1.5
# 2	6	9	2.25
# 3	10	15	3.75

P-shape print geometries

Case 1

Case 2

Case 3

AM printing with Juggerbot 3D (Tradesman Series P3-44)

- Used material: Wood fiber reinforced PLA (20 wt. %)
- Print speed: 1350, 848, and 425 mm/min
- Extrusion temperature: 165 °C
- Layer time: 90, 140, and 240 seconds

Juggerbot3D – Tradesman Series P33-44

Experimental setup

Transient heat transfer model using finite element analysis (FEA)

- Element activation
 - Activate elements when a tool path passes through the elements (tool path from Gcode).
 - Update boundary conditions (activate elements in extrusion temperature).
- Anisotropic thermal properties with printing direction
 - The fiber in the extruded substance is aligned with the tool path.
 - The principal direction (x -direction) is chosen as the print direction (z -direction = stacking direction).
- Layer height (number)
 - The element has the same height (number) as the real print to simulate the layer-by-layer stacking procedure.

FEA heat transfer model

- Temperature prediction for the P-shaped print
 - Temperature history is predicted over the entire process.
 - Temperature field is displayed as color maps, with hot areas in red and cold areas in blue.
- Material properties: Wood flour reinforced polylactic acid (WFPLA, 20wt.%)
 - **Density:** $1,240 \text{ kg/m}^3$, **Specific heat:** $1,476 \text{ J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$, **Conductivity** (x, y, z): $0.198, 0.186, 0.159 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

Simulation parameter calibration

1. Deposition temperature calibration

- Extruded material experiences rapid cooling and the simulation model lacks the ability to simulate this accurately.
- By comparing the temperature at the center of wall position when the layer deposition process is finished, the deposition temperature is calibrated.

2. Convection coefficient calibration

- By comparing the temperature profiles, the convection coefficient is calibrated.

Results: P-shape print case 1

- Case 1
 - # of thermal images: 5,140
 - Layer time: 90s → theoretical printing time for 60 layers: 5,400s
 - Overall printing time with IR camera (printing + thermocouple installation): 5,763s
 - Installation time (1st and 2nd): 177s and 200s
 - Printing time: 5,386s

Comparison of IR thermal data with simulation _Case 1

- Boundary conditions:

- Deposition temperature: 130 °C
- Boundary temperature: 28 °C
- Convection coefficient: 7
- Emissivity: 0.85

Results: P-shape print case 2

- Case 2
 - # of thermal images: 7,606
 - Layer time: 120s (1~15th) & 140s → theoretical printing time for 60 layers: 8,100s
 - Overall printing time with IR camera (printing + thermocouple installation): 8,764s
 - Installation time (1st and 2nd): 402s and 197s
 - Printing time: 8,165s

Comparison of IR thermal data with simulation _Case 2

- Boundary conditions:
 - Deposition temperature: 130 °C
 - Boundary temperature: 28 °C
 - Convection coefficient: 7
 - Emissivity: 0.85

Results: P-shape print case 3

- Case 3
 - # of thermal images: 14,771
 - Layer time: 275s → theoretical printing time for 60 layers: 16,500s
 - Overall printing time with IR camera (printing + thermocouple installation): 16,868s
 - Installation time (1st and 2nd): 225s and 170s
 - Printing time: 16,473s

Comparison of IR thermal data with simulation _Case 3

- Boundary conditions:
 - Deposition temperature: 130 °C
 - Boundary temperature: 28 °C
 - Convection coefficient: 7
 - Emissivity: 0.85

Objective 3:

Sensitivity analysis of thermal conductivity, heat capacity and thermal expansion coefficient on temperature and deformation history

Temperature and deformation measurement during wall print

- Experimental set up
 - Temperature measurement using an IR camera
 - Displace measurement using Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT)
 - Wall dimensions (L x W x H, m): 1.36 x 0.0153 x 0.3
 - Bead geometry (W x H, mm): 7.65 x 2.54

Experimental set up

IR image of 3D printing process (Temperature measure)

Warpage measurement with LVDT

Simulation model for temperature and deformation prediction

- Sequentially coupled thermomechanical model

- Step 1 (thermal simulation): transient heat transfer analysis is conducted to obtain the temperature field data by using the heat transfer element (e.g., DC3D8).
- Step 2 (structural simulation): Sequentially, the mechanical analysis is conducted to obtain the stress/deformation field based on the previously predicted temperature data by using the structural element (e.g., C3D8).

- Boundary conditions

Results of temperature prediction

- Temperature at the center of the wall was recorded and compared those from experiments and simulation model.
 - Total print time (10,800 seconds) was divided in 5 intervals.
 - Each time interval the temperature from basement to surface was measured.

Temperature field at different time interval

Comparison of temperature profile from experiments with those from simulation model.

Results of deformation prediction

- Deformations at the left and right corner was measured and compared those from experiments and simulation model.
 - The deformation is recorded during the whole printing process
 - In experiments, the length of left and right were different, so the deformation was unsymmetric.

Sensitivity test of thermal conductivity on temperature history

- Thermal conductivity was increased and decreased by 10%.

Sensitivity test of heat capacity on temperature history

- Heat capacity was increased and decreased by 10%.

Sensitivity test of thermal expansion on deformation history

- Coefficient of thermal expansion was increased and decreased by 10%.

Summary & Conclusion

- Effect of bead overlap distance on thermal conductivity was evaluated
 - Specimens were manufactured with varying overlap distances.
 - Thermal conductivity increased as the bead overlap distance increased, indicating greater contact surface area between beads.
- Effect of bead geometry on thermal history was investigated
 - P-shaped structures were printed with different bead geometries.
 - The cooling rate decreased with the increase in bead size due to the greater thermal mass. However, the transient heat transfer model accurately predicted the temperature history regardless of the bead geometry.
- Sensitivity analysis of thermal conductivity, heat capacity, and thermal expansion on temperature and deformation history was conducted.
 - Thermal conductivity and heat capacity have minimal effect on the thermal history.
 - In contrast, thermal expansion has a comparatively greater impact on the final deformation.

Other developments of simulation

Extrusion deposition additive manufacturing

Target Temperature: 145 °C

Process parameters optimizations

Manufacturing Process

Characterization (Mechanical)

Part Performance Evaluation

Process and Performance Optimization

In-situ Process Monitoring and Process Control

Performance simulations

Process monitoring and real time process control

Thank you!